

Work-Life Balance And Performance Of Faculty Members In Congressional District I, Batangas Province

Joyce Elenor P. Cueto¹
1 – Golden Gate Colleges
elenorjoyce@gmail.com / 0009-0006-2672-1158

Publication Date: May 23, 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20353966](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20353966)

Abstract

Faculty members in higher education often face heavy instructional and administrative demands that may affect their ability to sustain a healthy work-life balance and maintain high teaching performance.

This study assessed the extent of manifestation of faculty members' work-life balance (time management, job satisfaction, and involvement balance), determined the level of their teaching performance (planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibilities), identified challenges in maintaining both, and tested the relationship between work-life balance and teaching performance.

The study employed a descriptive quantitative design using a validated, researcher-made survey questionnaire. Respondents were 172 full-time faculty members selected through stratified random sampling from a population of 307 in higher education institutions within Congressional District I, Batangas Province. Data were analyzed using weighted mean for descriptive interpretation and Pearson product-moment correlation (r) for relationship testing, with statistical processing via SPSS.

Faculty work-life balance was moderately manifested while teaching performance was rated high. A significant positive relationship was found between work-life balance and teaching performance. Challenges reported by the faculty members included administrative workload, compromised personal life, and burnout due to constant role demands.

Findings indicate that improving faculty work-life balance is associated with better teaching performance. Institutional support that reduces administrative burden and strengthens time management and wellness initiatives may help sustain high performance while protecting faculty well-being.

Keywords: *work-life balance, teaching performance, job satisfaction, involvement balance, time management, higher education.*

Introduction

Work-life balance is increasingly recognized as vital for sustaining teachers' motivation, well-being, and effectiveness. Faculty members in higher education often manage overlapping responsibilities such as lesson planning, grading, administrative work, mentoring, and institutional duties, which frequently extend beyond regular work hours. This imbalance can contribute to stress, reduced satisfaction, and burnout factors that can also affect the quality of classroom instruction and student learning experiences.

In the Philippine higher education context, faculty members commonly juggle professional responsibilities alongside personal obligations, making work-life balance difficult to maintain. Supportive work environments and institutional policies are essential in promoting faculty well being and sustaining effective performance.

Work-life balance is commonly understood as an inter-role phenomenon that reflects an individual's orientation across multiple life roles. The study was guided by Work-Life Balance Theory, the Job Demands Resources (JD-R) Model, and Role Theory, which collectively explain how job demands, available resources, and competing roles influence faculty well-being and performance.

Related literature indicates that excessive workloads and time pressures increase stress and reduce well-being, while adequate organizational support can mitigate burnout and sustain productivity. Teaching performance is often linked to readiness and planning, classroom environment management, effective instruction, and fulfillment of professional responsibilities.

This study examined work-life balance and teaching performance of faculty members in higher education institutions within Congressional District I, Batangas Province. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of manifestation of faculty members' work-life balance in terms of time management, job satisfaction, and involvement balance?
2. How may the level of performance of faculty members be assessed in terms of planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibilities?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the assessments on faculty members' work-life balance and their level of performance?
4. What challenges do faculty members face in maintaining work-life balance and good performance?
5. Based on the results, what intervention activities may be proposed?

Objectives of the Study

The study aimed to:

1. Assess faculty work-life balance across time management, job satisfaction, and involvement balance;
2. Assess faculty teaching performance across planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, and professional responsibilities;
3. Determine the relationship between work-life balance and teaching performance;
4. Identify challenges affecting work-life balance and performance; and
5. Propose intervention activities based on the findings.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between faculty members' work-life balance and teaching performance.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive quantitative research design using survey questionnaires to gather data on faculty work-life balance and teaching performance.

Participants

Respondents were drawn from a total population of 307 full-time faculty members in Congressional District I, Batangas Province. Using a 5% margin of error, a sample of 172 faculty members was determined and selected through stratified random sampling to ensure proportional representation per institution.

Instruments

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was developed based on related literature and relevant instruments. The tool included Likert-scale items covering work-life balance in terms of time management, job satisfaction, involvement balance, the performance of faculty members in terms of their planning and preparation, classroom environment, instruction, professional responsibilities and the challenges faced by faculty members affecting their work-life balance and performance. The instrument underwent expert content validation and pilot testing. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, and refinements were incorporated prior to full administration.

Procedure

Approval was obtained from institutional authorities prior to data collection. The questionnaire was distributed to identified respondents in printed or digital form. Informed consent

was secured, and confidentiality and anonymity were ensured. Responses were collected, encoded, and securely stored for analysis.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using weighted mean for descriptive interpretation and Pearson product-moment correlation (r) to determine the relationship between work-life balance and teaching performance. Frequency and ranking were also utilized where appropriate. Statistical processing was performed using SPSS.

Results

This section presents the key descriptive and inferential findings of the study. Tables 1-5 summarize the descriptive and inferential results of the study.

Table 1. Work-life Balance of Faculty Members by Dimension

Dimension	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Time Management	3.10	Moderately Manifested
Job Satisfaction	3.25	Moderately Manifested
Involvement Balance	3.12	Moderately Manifested

Table 2. Teaching Performance of Faculty Members by Dimension

Dimension	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Planning and Preparation	3.99	High
Classroom Environment	3.82	High
Instruction	3.93	High
Professional Responsibilities	3.80	High

Table 3. Top Challenges Faced by Faculty Members

Indicator (Challenge)	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Overwhelmed by volume of administrative tasks	3.75	Strongly Agree
Personal life often compromised by professional duties	3.63	Strongly Agree
Experience burnout due to constant demands of role	3.60	Strongly Agree
Struggle to maintain work-life balance due to faculty responsibilities	3.55	Strongly Agree

Table 4. Correlation Between Overall Work-life Balance and Performance

Variables	r value	p value	Decision
Overall Work-life Balance vs Overall Performance	0.485	0.000	Reject Ho (Significant)

Table 5. Correlation Between Work-life Balance Dimensions and Performance Dimensions

WLB Dimension	Performance Dimension	r value	p value	Interpretation
Time Management	Planning and Preparation	.650	.000	Strong positive
Time Management	Classroom Environment	.520	.000	Strong positive
Time Management	Instruction	.700	.000	Strong positive
Time Management	Professional Responsibilities	.760	.000	Very strong positive
Job Satisfaction	Planning and Preparation	.600	.000	Strong positive
Job Satisfaction	Classroom Environment	.680	.000	Strong positive
Job Satisfaction	Instruction	.650	.000	Strong positive
Job Satisfaction	Professional Responsibilities	.580	.000	Strong positive
Involvement Balance	Planning and Preparation	.720	.000	Strong positive
Involvement Balance	Classroom Environment	.630	.000	Strong positive
Involvement Balance	Instruction	.750	.000	Strong positive
Involvement Balance	Professional Responsibilities	.690	.000	Strong positive

Descriptive statistics

Work-life balance (extent of manifestation):

- Time Management: Composite mean = 3.10 (Moderately Manifested)
- Job Satisfaction: Composite mean = 3.25 (Moderately Manifested)
- Involvement Balance: Composite mean = 3.12 (Moderately Manifested)

Teaching performance (level of performance):

- Planning and Preparation: Composite mean = 3.99 (High)
- Classroom Environment: Composite mean = 3.82 (High)
- Instruction: Composite mean = 3.93 (High)
- Professional Responsibilities: Composite mean = 3.80 (High)

Challenges faced by faculty members:

- Overall challenges: Composite mean = 3.44 (Agree)
- Overwhelmed by administrative tasks: WM = 3.75
- Personal life compromised by professional duties: WM = 3.63
- Burnout due to constant role demands: WM = 3.60

Inferential statistics

A statistically significant positive relationship was found between overall work-life balance and overall teaching performance ($r = 0.485$, $p = 0.000$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Selected relationships between work-life balance dimensions and performance dimensions (all $p = 0.000$):

- Time Management vs Planning and Preparation: $r = .650$
- Time Management vs Classroom Environment: $r = .520$
- Time Management vs Instruction: $r = .700$
- Time Management vs Professional Responsibilities: $r = .760$
- Job Satisfaction vs Planning and Preparation: $r = .600$
- Job Satisfaction vs Classroom Environment: $r = .680$
- Job Satisfaction vs Instruction: $r = .650$
- Job Satisfaction vs Professional Responsibilities: $r = .580$
- Involvement Balance vs Planning and Preparation: $r = .720$
- Involvement Balance vs Classroom Environment: $r = .630$
- Involvement Balance vs Instruction: $r = .750$
- Involvement Balance vs Professional Responsibilities: $r = .690$

Discussion

Faculty members reported moderately manifested work-life balance yet high teaching performance. This pattern suggests that performance may be maintained despite role strain, possibly through extended work hours and personal sacrifice. The significant positive correlations indicate that better work-life balance especially in time management and involvement balance is associated with stronger instructional delivery and more effective fulfillment of professional responsibilities.

The results align with the JD-R model, which explains how high job demands (e.g., administrative workload and time pressure) can strain well-being unless balanced by resources

and supports. They also reflect Role Theory, highlighting stress arising from competing professional and personal roles.

The findings support institutional actions that protect faculty well-being while sustaining high performance. A Work-Life Integration Program is proposed, focusing on:

1. Structural interventions that streamline or reduce administrative burdens
2. Time management and boundary-setting strategies
3. Wellness and psychological support to reduce stress and prevent burnout

These interventions may help maintain teaching quality by improving workload distribution, strengthening recovery time, and supporting faculty resilience.

The study was limited to higher education institutions in Congressional District I, Batangas Province, and findings may not be generalizable to other contexts. Data were self-reported and may be subject to response biases. The data collection period was confined to a specific academic year, and other contributing factors (e.g., compensation, career advancement, and broader institutional variables) were not examined in depth.

Conclusion

Faculty members demonstrated moderately manifested work-life balance but high teaching performance. Work-life balance showed a significant positive relationship with teaching performance, indicating that improvements in balance are associated with better and more sustainable professional output. The most pressing challenges were administrative workload, compromised personal life, and burnout risk.

Based on the findings, the study recommends:

1. Streamlining administrative tasks to reduce workload burden
2. Establishing clearer work-time boundaries and supportive institutional policies
3. Providing accessible wellness and psychological support programs
4. Offering professional development on time management and work-life integration
5. Conducting further studies (including longitudinal and qualitative approaches) to evaluate changes following interventions

References

- Ahmed, G., Tayyub, M., & Ismail, R. (2020). Effects of classroom environment for improving students' learning at secondary level in Punjab Province, Pakistan. *Sci Academique*, 1(1), 2–15.
- Berglund, E., Anderzén, I., Andersén, Å., et al. (2021). Work-life balance predicted work ability two years later: A cohort study of employees in the Swedish energy and water sector. *BMC Public Health*, 21, 1212. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11235-4>
- Cho, H., Pyun, D. Y., & Wang, C. K. J. (2023). Teachers' work-life balance: The effect of work leisure conflict on work-related outcomes. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2023.2259113>
- Diego-Medrano, E., & Salazar, L. R. (2021). Examining the work-life balance of faculty in higher education. *International Journal of Social Policy and Education*, 3(3), 27–36.
- Duran, E. P., Pontillas, P. V., & Comon, J. D. (2024). Teachers' work-life balance and well-being across Opol East District, Division of Misamis Oriental. *European Modern Studies Journal*, 8(4), 134–166. [https://doi.org/10.59573/emsj.8\(4\).2024.9](https://doi.org/10.59573/emsj.8(4).2024.9)
- Francisco, C. D. C., & Celon, L. C. (2020). Teachers' instructional practices and its effects on students' academic performance. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Multidisciplinary Studies*, 6(7), 64–71.
- Janib, J., Rasdi, R. M., Omar, Z., Alias, S. N., Zaremohzzabieh, Z., & Ahrari, S. (2021). The relationship between workload and performance of research university academics in Malaysia: The mediating effects of career commitment and job satisfaction. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 17(2), 85–99. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v17i2.13394>
- Khatimah, H. (2021). Major impact of classroom environment in students' learning. *Journal of Education Review Provision*, 1(1), 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.55885/jerp.v1i1.42>
- Obina, W. F., Ndibazza, J., Kabanda, R., Musana, J., & Nanyingi, M. (2024). Factors associated with perceived work-life balance among health workers in Gulu District, Northern Uganda: A health facility-based cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 278. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-17776-8>
- Pido, M. R., Mahmud, M., & Sudirman, S. (2023). Teacher performance on student learning outcomes. *Journal of Economic and Business Education*, 1(1), 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.37479/jebe.v1i1.16928>
- Rusticus, S. A., Pashootan, T., & Mah, A. (2023). What are the key elements of a positive

- learning environment? Perspectives from students and faculty. *Learning Environments Research*, 26(1), 161–175. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-022-09410-4>
- Wahab, O. S., & Arazo, V. H. (2024). Quality of work-life balance among teachers and their performance in face-to-face classes. *Psych Educ*, 21(5), 528–543. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12594312>
- Wei, C., & Ye, J. H. (2022). The impacts of work-life balance on the emotional exhaustion and well-being of college teachers in China. *Healthcare*, 10(11), 2234.
- Commission on Higher Education. (2008). Manual of regulations for private higher education (CHED Memorandum Order No. 40, s. 2008). <https://ched.gov.ph>
- Commission on Higher Education. (2021). CHED strategic plan for higher education 2021–2025. <https://ched.gov.ph>
- Congress of the Philippines. (1966). Republic Act No. 4670: Magna Carta for public school teachers. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph>
- Congress of the Philippines. (2009). Republic Act No. 9710: Magna Carta of women. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph>
- Government of the Philippines. (1974). Labor Code of the Philippines (Presidential Decree No. 442, as amended). <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph>